

Adducts of Hetero Diorganotin Dichlorides with Amines

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There is a considerable current interest in the organotin coordination chemistry. Recently diorganotin dihalides have been shown to act as Lewis acids and their adducts with Lewis bases have been studied extensively^{1,2,3}. The adducts with diorganotin dichlorides having dissimilar alkyl groups which have not been isolated so far, have been selected for the present attempt.

The required dichlorides of tin with dissimilar alkyl groups as $C_6H_5(n-C_4H_9)SnCl_2$, $C_6H_5(C_2H_5)SnCl_2$ and $C_6H_5(C_6H_5CH_2)SnCl_2$ have been prepared in this laboratory by the methods of Frederic Barry Kipping⁴ and Ralph H. Bullard and Francis R. Holden⁵ with slight modification⁶. Amines as, pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, α , β , γ picolines, morpholine, aniline and piperidine have been selected for complexing with the above prepared Lewis acids. The adducts of $C_6H_5(n-C_4H_9)SnCl_2$ and $C_6H_5(C_2H_5)SnCl_2$ have been separated with petroleum ether while those of $C_6H_5(C_6H_5CH_2)SnCl_2$ with carbon tetrachloride. A brief description of these adducts is recorded in the table.

With the exception of aniline complexes, all others are white solids with generally sharp melting points. The stoichiometry of these complexes (1 : 2) has been established from the tin and halogen contents. In all these complexes tin appears to exist in hexavalent form which suggests the octahedral configuration as has been reported in similar complexes earlier too². Conductometric titrations of the Lewis bases with Lewis acids in nitrobenzene at 25° have further supported the formation of 1 : 2 coordination complexes in all these cases. The values of molar conductances of these complexes determined in nitrobenzene as solvent at 25° fall mainly in the range of 1–10 $cm^2\ ohm^{-1}\ mole^{-1}$, whereas the values required for uni-univalent electrolytes in nitrobenzene solvent are required to be quite close to 20 $cm^2\ ohm^{-1}\ mole^{-1}$. This suggests that there is no possibility of these complexes being ionic.

The i.r. spectra of these complexes have been studied in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} on Perkin Elmer 337 spectrophotometer. The far i.r. studies which due to lack of facilities are still pending may probably be more helpful to explain the exact nature of these compounds and enable us to determine their structure.

1. R. J. H. Clark, Alwyn G. Davies and R. J. Puddephatt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1828.
2. Gen-Etsu Matsubayashi, Toshio Tanaka and Rokuro Okawa, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1831.
3. I. R. Beattie and G. P. Macquillan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1519.
4. Frederic Barry Kipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2365.
5. Ralph H. Bullard and Francis R. Holden, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 3150.
6. K. L. Jaura, L. K. Churamani and K. K. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 329.

TABLE

Sr. No.	Adducts	m.pt. °C	Δ Molar conductance $\text{cm}^2 \text{ohm}^{-1}$ mole ⁻¹	% of Cl		% of Tin	
				Found	Required	Found	Required
1.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_1$	78—79	4.50	14.25	14.73	24.25	24.68
2.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_2$	74—75	5.93	11.83	12.19	20.95	20.44
3.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_3$	114—15	3.24	11.81	12.19	20.04	20.44
4.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_4$	75—76	16.87	13.65	13.92	23.02	23.33
5.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_5$	73—74	7.05	13.65	13.92	22.99	23.33
6.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_6$	133—34	5.60	13.60	13.92	22.85	23.33
7.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_7$	135—37	8.30	13.97	14.25	23.50	23.89
8.	* $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_8$	73—75	—	13.59	13.92	22.88	23.33
9.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_9$	148—51	2.07	14.10	14.37	23.65	24.08
10.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_1$	88—90	3.89	15.25	15.60	25.82	26.21
11.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_2$	95—96	9.08	12.62	12.81	22.05	21.48
12.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_3$	114—16	3.85	13.10	12.81	21.03	21.48
13.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_4$	73—75	10.88	15.12	14.73	25.12	24.68
14.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_5$	88	4.73	15.21	14.73	24.23	24.68
15.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_6$	96—98	9.74	14.92	14.73	24.17	24.08
16.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_7$	112—14	6.51	15.00	15.11	24.93	25.32
17.	* $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_8$	90	—	14.43	14.73	24.06	24.68
18.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_9$	(Decomposed) 160—65	2.59	15.56	15.23	25.09	25.53
19.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_1$	112—14	3.50	13.39	13.75	22.72	23.06
20.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_2$	90—91	4.75	11.21	11.52	18.85	19.32
21.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_3$	120—23	6.40	11.32	11.52	18.97	19.32
22.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_4$	70—75	13.72	12.56	13.05	21.97	21.87
23.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_5$	120—23	6.87	22.95	13.05	21.34	21.87
24.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_6$	88—92	14.20	12.83	13.05	21.50	21.87
25.	* $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_7$	133—35	—	13.45	13.34	21.97	22.36
26.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_22\text{L}_8$	112—15	0.81	12.53	13.05	21.35	21.27

$\text{L}_1 = \text{Pyridine}$,

$\text{L}_2 = \text{Quinoline}$,

$\text{L}_3 = \text{Isoquinoline}$,

$\text{L}_4 = \alpha\text{-Picoline}$,

$\text{L}_5 = \beta\text{-Picoline}$,

$\text{L}_6 = \gamma\text{-Picoline}$

$\text{L}_7 = \text{Morpholine}$,

$\text{L}_8 = \text{Aniline}$,

$\text{L}_9 = \text{Piperidine}$.

* The molar conductance could not be determined as the complexes were not soluble in nitrobenzene.

A comprehensive paper with proposed structure of these complexes would be submitted at a later stage when all the investigations are complete.

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